

Zinc Contaminate on Urban Roadside in Rush Hour, Bangkok, Thailand

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Abstract : This research aims to study the Zinc (Zn) concentration in fine particulate matter on Rajchawithee roadside in rush hour. 30 Samples were collected in Jun to August 2013 by 8 stage non-avaible cascade impactor. Each samples (filter paper) were digest with nitric acid and analyed by atomic absorption spectrophotometer for Zinc determination. The highest value for the mean fraction (18.00 ± 9.28 %) is the size 9.0 - 110.0 micron follow by the range 3.3 - 4.7 micron (14.77 ± 14.66 %) and 1.1 - 2.1 micron (14.01 ± 11.77 %). The concentration of Zn in the particulate matter of range 0.43 - 0.7 μm , 0.7 - 1.1 μm , 1.1 - 2.1 μm , 2.1 - 3.3 μm , 3.3 - 4.7 μm , 4.7 - 5.8 μm , 5.8 - 9.0 μm , 9.0 - 10.0 μm , were 41.56 - 217.62 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (175.86 ± 32.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 152.60 - 217.24 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (187.71 ± 17.42 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 142.90 - 214.67 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (180.95 ± 18.71 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 155.48 - 218.19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (183.22 ± 19.94 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 151.72 - 217.39 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (181.85 ± 17.57 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 133.86 - 220.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (178.78 ± 23.45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 160.00 - 220.35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (182.58 ± 18.08 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 153.30 - 226.70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (181.52 ± 20.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), repectively. The Zn concentration in each size of particulate matter was not statistically significant different ($p > .005$)

Keywords : air pollution, particulate matter, size distribution, zinc

Conference Title : ICEBESE 2014 : International Conference on Environmental, Biological, Ecological Sciences and Engineering

Conference Location : Prague, Czech Republic

Conference Dates : July 10-11, 2014